

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SIMPLE RP-HPLC METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF DOXAZOSIN MESYLATE

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ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate, reproducible and sensitive method for the determination of Doxazosin Mesilate was developed and validated. Doxazosin Mesilate was separated by HPLC using a LiChrospher® RP-18 column and isocratic elution with a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. A mixture of Acetonitrile with Buffer solution (pH=3.9) (45:55) was used as the mobile phase. The detection was at 330 nm wavelength. The proposed method was validated for linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection and limit of quantification. The linear range of determination for Doxazosin was 0.04-0.13 mg/ml. The percentage recovery of Doxazosin was obtained from a range of 99.50-101.5%. The developed method is suitable for routine quality control analysis of a titled drug or combination of tablet formulation.

Keywords: doxazosin mesilate, alpha-1 adrenoceptor, analysis, RP-HPLC.

Introduction

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), or an enlarged prostate, is a very common condition, mostly affecting men over the age of 50, although it can also occur at an earlier age. It is expressed in a benign growth of normal cells from the prostate, which increase in number and the volume of the gland becomes larger. Drug therapy usually begins with conservative treatment. The aim is to relieve complaints, slow the progression of the condition and reduce the likelihood of surgery. Most often, a combination of an alpha1-blocker and a phytopreparation, or an alpha1-blocker and 5-alpha-reductase inhibitors, is used. Combination therapy includes both alpha blockers and 5-alpha-reductase inhibitors.

Doxazosin Mesilate (DZS) is 1-(4-Amino-6,7-dimethoxyquinazolin-2-yl)-4-[(2RS)-2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzodioxin-2-ylcarbonyl]piperazine methanesulphonate (Figure 1). Doxazosin Mesilate [1, 2] is a selective alpha-1 adrenoceptor. It is used to treat high blood pressure or symptoms due to an enlarged prostate in men. Alpha1-blockers relax the smooth muscles of the blood vessels, prostate gland and bladder. These drugs are not effective for all men and may cause side effects dizziness, fatigue and confusion. Administration of doxazosin in patients with symptomatic benign hyperplasia (BPH) significantly improves urodynamics and symptoms. The effect in DPH is thought to be the result of selective blockade of alpha-adrenoceptors located in the muscular stroma and capsule of the prostate and bladder neck. Doxazosin is an effective blocker of the 1A subtype of alpha-1-adrenoceptors, which account for over 70% of the subtypes in the prostate. This applies to the action in patients with DPH. Doxazosin selectively and competitively blocks postsynaptic alpha-1-adrenergic receptors, which causes peripheral vasodilation.

Doxazosin alone or in combination with other drugs is reported to be estimated by spectrophotometric method [3-5], HPLC [6-7], ion-pair chromatography

[8], LC-MS [9], micellar electrokinetic chromatography [10], HPTLC [11], FT-IR [12].

Fig. 1: Structure of Doxazosin Mesilate

The work aim is to develop a simple and accurate method for routine analysis, this study describes the HPLC-UV method, for the determination of this drug. Validation of the current method is performed according to the requirements of the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline [13].

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

The Doxazosin Mesilate CRS reference standard was obtained from Sigma Aldrich. A tablet formulation containing Doxazosin Mesilate 4 mg was obtained commercially. HPLC grade Acetonitrile was procured from Merck Ltd. All other chemical reagents - Sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate R, (NaH₂PO₄·H₂O), o-fosforic acid 85% (m/m) H₃PO₄ were of analytical grade.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions

HPLC analysis was performed by isocratic elution with a flow rate 1.0 ml/min. A high performance liquid chromatographic system (SHIMADZU Corporation, LC-20 AD quaternary pump) with an auto sampler, Shimadzu DGU-20A₅ vacuum degasser and a Shimadzu SPD-20A UV/VIS detector was used for analysis. The data was recorded using Lab Solutions Software. Separation was carried out at 30°C, using LiChrospher® RP-18 (250 x 4.6 mm) column packed with octadecylsilyl silica gel 5 µm. The detector was set at 330 nm. The chromatogram is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Typical chromatogram of Doxazosin Mesilate

Preparation of Mobile Phase

The mobile phase (1000 ml) was prepared by mixing of Acetonitrile and Buffer solution (pH=3.9) (45:55). The mobile phase was sonicated for 10 min and then it was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter paper.

Preparation of Buffer Solution

0.138 g of Sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate were dissolved into 1000 ml of water, and adjusted pH to 3.9 with o-phosphoric acid.

Preparation of Standard Solution

400 mg Doxazosin working standard (accurately weighed) was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. After the addition of about 50 ml mobile phase, the mixture was sonicated for about 10 min and made up to the volume. The stock solution was suitably diluted to produce a concentration of 0.04 mg/ml of Doxazosin.

Sample Preparation

Twenty tablets were weighed, finely powdered and the average weight was determined. A portion of powder equivalent to 40 mg Doxazosin was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and 50 ml of mobile phase was added and sonicated for 10 minutes to effect complete dissolution. The suspension was then made up to volume with a mobile phase and filtered. The aliquot portion of the filtrate was further diluted to get a final concentration of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Doxazosin. 20 μl of the test solution was injected, a chromatogram was recorded and the amount of the drug was calculated.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary experiments were conducted to determine the chromatographic conditions for the best separation and quantification of DZS. The column chemistry, solvent selectivity, detection wavelength, and flow

rate were studied and optimized. A reversed-phase column LiChrospher[®] RP-18, 250 x 4.6 mm; particle size, 5 μm with an isocratic mobile phase (45:55 %v/v mixture of acetonitrile and phosphate buffer) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min were found to provide adequate analytical performance in a short run time. The buffer pH was adjusted to 3.9 ± 0.02 with phosphoric acid. The total chromatographic analysis time per sample was 8 min with DZS eluting at a retention time of 7.2 min.

The developed method for determination of Doxazosin was further validated by using the following parameters:

Selectivity

Selectivity of the current method was demonstrated by good separation of the active ingredient (DZS). Furthermore, matrix components, e.g. excipients, do not interfere with the analyte.

Linearity

Standard solutions containing Doxazosin (0.04-0.13 mg/ml) were prepared in the mobile phase. Linearity of Doxazosin is determined at 330 nm by testing five concentrations of Reference solution in the range from 50 to 150% of the target value, i.e. from 0.04 to 0.13 mg/ml. Each concentration is injected in triplicate. The area of each peak was plotted against the concentration to obtain the calibration graph (Figure 3). The five concentrations of each solution were subjected to regression analysis to calculate the calibration equation and correlation coefficients. The results obtained are shown in Table 1 and show that the current method was linear for the analyte in the range specified above with correlation coefficients better than 0.999.

Table 1

Linearity data for Doxazosin		
Level, %	Concentration (mg/ml)	Area
50	0.044	3593804
100	0.066	5347706
150	0.087	6887608
200	0.109	8834510
250	0.131	10379412
Correlation Coefficient		0.999
Slope (mAU*s):		7.994E7
Intercept:		2520.4 (0.04% of area at 100% level)
Acceptance criteria:		r>0.996
Intercept:		≤ 3% (of area at 100% level).

Fig. 3: Linearity graph of Doxazosin

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ were experimentally verified by six injections of Doxazosin at the appropriate concentrations. The LOD was calculated to be 0.03 µg/ml and the LOQ was calculated to be 0.6 µg/ml.

Precision

The system precision of this method was evaluated by calculating the %RSD of the peak areas of six replicate injections of the standard solution, which was found to be 0.704 %. For method precision evaluated with six sample replicate injections were found to be 0.841% for Doxazosin and it was found to be less than 1.0% shown in the Table 2.

Table 2

Results of precision for Doxazosin	
Precision	Doxazosin
Mean value, mg	3.98
System Precision, % RSD	0.704
Method Precision, %RSD	0.841

Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was calculated by recovery studies. It is carried out by preparing samples of 50%, 100% and 150% of the target concentration. The samples were prepared in triplicate at each level. The results of the studies along with its evaluation are given in Table 3.

Table 4

Results of recovery studies for Doxazosin						
Sample	Recovery	Amount present	Amount recovered	% recovered	SD	%RSD
Doxazosin	50%	2.0 mg	1.99	99.50	1.528	1.731
	100%	4.0 mg	3.98	99.50	1.089	1.102
	150%	6.0 mg	6.09	101.5	1.968	0.865

CONCLUSION

An simple, accurate, sensitive and precise HPLC method with UV detection for the estimation of Doxazosin was developed and validated for quality control analysis in tablets. The proposed method is rapid, where the total analytical run time is less than 8 min and shows high degree of accuracy and precision with less than 2 % RSD. It is convenient for laboratory quality control of tablet dosage forms containing the determined substance.

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